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HARVESTING ALTERNATIVE ENERGY: EXPLORING EXERGY, HUMAN POWER, ANIMAL BODY HEAT, AND NOISE AS SUSTAINABLE SOURCES

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Abstract

The excessive use of non-renewable fossil fuels has led to a pressing energy crisis that demands urgent attention. While renewable sources like solar, wind, and water have gained significant attention as alternatives, we must explore additional avenues. This study takes an interdisciplinary approach, investigating the potential of waste streams from energy production and other untapped natural sources as sustainable energy solutions. Through a review of case studies, this study demonstrates how these alternative sources, including human power, animal body heat, and noise, can seamlessly integrate into architecture and urban planning. This article first discusses passive design strategies integrating alternative energy sources into vernacular architecture. Then, it reviews the waste stream (exergy) and potential energy sources, such as human power, animal body heat, and noise, in contemporary proposals and case studies. It demonstrates how an alternative energy design strategy may easily incorporate these many sources into our architecture and urban planning through passive and active design strategies to increase the energy efficiency of our built environment.

Keywords: Alternative energy sources, energy exchange, human and animal power, potential energy sources, waste stream.

1 INTRODUCTION

The world is currently struggling with a threatening energy crisis due to the depletion of fossil fuels, which have long served as the primary energy source (Yazdandoust et al., 2023). To effectively address this crisis, it is projected that by 2050, one-third of the world's energy needs must be met through alternative sources (Shi, 2013). While renewable energy derived from sources like sunlight, wind, and water has garnered significant attention, it is imperative to recognize that a diverse array of alternative energy sources exists within our environment. One notable example is the exergy found within the unidirectional flow of our primary energy systems. Often, a portion of this energy is dissipated as heat or other forms, constituting a potentially valuable resource that can be recaptured and reintegrated into the energy cycle through astute design strategies. Additionally, energy can be harnessed from various potential sources spanning mechanical, electrical, chemical, and even biological domains, encompassing humans and animals.

Vernacular architecture can teach valuable lessons about how our predecessors efficiently tapped into accessible alternate energy sources. Vernacular architecture is the term used to describe traditional and indigenous building design and construction methods that have developed geographic areas and reflect the local climate, culture, materials available, and social necessities. It is frequently described as practical, adaptable, and appropriate for the local area. They skillfully capture natural energies and alter them to meet

various requirements. In contemporary architecture, the predominant reliance on non-renewable fossil fuels persists, yet with rapid technological advancements, the integration of potential alternative energy sources has become increasingly viable. This study briefly overviews the creative approaches in vernacular architecture, illuminating how alternate energy was successfully harnessed. The topic of waste stream (exergy) is next explored, and various potential energy sources are introduced, including noise, animal and human power, and waste stream. Accompanied by illustrative case studies, this paper underscores their practical applications in both architectural and urban design contexts. The aim is to underscore the transformative potential of incorporating these alternative energy sources into our built environments, indicating a more sustainable and resilient future.

2 HARNESSING ALTERNATIVE ENERGY IN VERNACULAR ARCHITECTURE

Vernacular architecture offers a wealth of examples showcasing the integration of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power. A prime illustration is the courtyard building typology, addressed by Werner Blaser as one of humanity's earliest sophisticated architectural forms. Found across various climate zones, it mitigates diverse climatic conditions, serving as a sun collector or shield (Fig.1) (Passe et al., 2015).

However, astute passive techniques in traditional architecture utilizing primary alternative energy sources have been underrepresented in scholarly discourse. Notably, livestock were ingeniously employed as a source of thermal energy. In Alpine regions, cattle were positioned along the outer periphery of structures to impart warmth to the surrounding space, leaving the interior, where humans resided, at a comfortable temperature (Hensel, 2008). A similar tactic was employed by Kurdish communities in western Iran, as depicted in Fig.2, where habitable spaces were situated above the animal shelter, benefiting from the natural warmth emitted by the livestock (Horne, 1981, pp.27-64).

Fig 1: Chinese courtyards change significantly in proportion between southern tropical and northern colder locations (Passe et al., 2015).

Fig 2. A courtyard house to the south of Kurdistan in Luristan. An animal shelter is dug out below the house, and the roof is used for various domestic activities (Horne, 1981).

Fig 3: Section through a taba Khana shows the movement of heated air from the hollow oven through the subfloor chamber and out the chimney built into the wall. The kitchen is on the left, and the living room is on the right (Horne, 1981).

Furthermore, kitchen waste heat was ingeniously repurposed to warm living spaces. A case in point is a house in Vale de Igreja, Beira Alta region, where bedrooms and alcoves, with limited external windows, were strategically arranged around the kitchen to harness its generated heat. Due to the scarcity of wood, families would retire to bed promptly after meals to conserve energy (Fernandes et al., 2012). In Afghanistan, an ingenious subfloor heating system warms specially designed living rooms called "taba khanas." Illustrated in Fig. 3, air heated by a recessed cooking oven circulates through intricate stone-lined passages beneath the floor before being expelled through a wall chimney. This design proves highly efficient in preserving cooking heat (Horne, 1981). The harnessing of natural environmental resources has been a practice since antiquity, exemplified by the invention of windmills and waterwheels (Shi, 2013). Windmills convert wind energy into mechanical work, performing grain milling and water pumping (Fig.4) (Historicallranweb, 2022).

Fig 4. Persian Windmills, plan, and section (Historicallranweb, 2022).

3 HARNESSING WASTE STREAMS (EXERGY) AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOURCE OF ENERGY

Waste heat, arising from processes involving fuel combustion or chemical reactions, is released into the environment (Loibl et al., 2017). Remarkably, between 20% to 50% of the primary energy input in the industrial sector is squandered as heat. Repurposing industrial waste heat within densely populated urban areas presents a pivotal strategy for enhancing urban energy efficiency. While high-grade heat exchange between industries, which refers to the heat transfer between systems at high-temperature levels, is a well-established method for achieving deep decarbonization, the potential of utilizing medium- and low-grade heat to regulate temperatures in densely populated urban spaces offer a promising avenue for substantial energy efficiency gains. European national studies suggest that waste heat has the technical capacity to meet 31% of the total heating demand for European buildings (Tong et al., 2017).

STEP 01: reduce energy consumption through insulation + by balancing heat and cold demanding program

PROGRAM

Fig 5: Program for the energy-balanced, multifunctional zone. Motorstraat's vision[11].

To harness energy from waste heat, the conventional urban planning paradigm must evolve towards a new approach that involves dismantling the zoning of single-function areas in favor of a harmonious, multifaceted urban framework. Within a multifunctional city block incorporating retail spaces, parking facilities, and small-scale housing, the waste heat generated in shopping areas and refrigeration systems can be redirected for residential use (Kuismanen, 2008). This approach is currently being applied in revitalizing Hart Van Zuid in Rotterdam, transforming it into an energy-balanced, multifunctional zone. Motorstraat's vision is to construct two new educational institutions along the redeveloped Motor Street (Fig5, 6). This integration with housing enhances social cohesion by ensuring constant use of the area throughout the day, with the addition of office spaces further reinforcing this diverse mix. The proposed 50 m Hart van Zuid swimming pool could be coupled with a new ice rink to achieve an energy equilibrium within this cluster. By combining the waste heat from the ice rink with the swimming pool's consistent demand for warmth, thermal storage can be employed to achieve energy balance. Any residual heating needs can be met by combining solar collectors and greenhouses (REAP, 2009).

Fig: 6: Steps 01 and 02: Summer energy demand situation. Step 03: Sustainably generated demand (REAP, 2009).

Adopting multifunctional spatial planning and configurations fosters energy equilibrium in cities, districts, and neighborhoods and reduces reliance on primary energy sources at the individual building scale. Reimagining building layouts empowers businesses to optimize their heating and cooling systems. For instance, placing staff rooms adjacent to in-house bakeries in a supermarket chain directly transfers waste heat from the oven to warm staff areas during breaks. Moreover, the surplus cold generated by freezers can be utilized in refrigeration units by strategically relocating cold and frozen food sections. Given the inefficiency of current building management practices, the buildings sector must invest further in this area to enhance energy efficiency through improved layout design. According to the Construction Products Association, many businesses exceed their projected expenditures on heating and cooling (Stoeglehner, 2020).

4 UNLOCKING HUMAN AND ANIMAL POWER ENERGY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOURCE OF ENERGY

4.1 Human Power

Fig 8: Left: Paris marathon energy harvesting path; right: people-powered football pitch (Wawrla, et al., 2018)

Fig7: Pavegen energy harvesting walkway (Wawrla et al, 2018).

The energy content of the human body is substantial. A person's body fat deposits can store as much energy as a one-ton battery, and a person walking 7500 steps a day can store as much energy as a 0.40 mAh battery rated at 1.2 V per month. Depending on the kind of exercise, the entire human body has been calculated to dissipate between 60 and 180 W (Cicchella, 2023). Human power encompasses both active and passive forms of energy generation. Active forms of energy are when users are involved in specific tasks to power electronic devices in their active iteration. In contrast, passive human power involves harvesting energy from everyday actions like walking, breathing, body heat, and motion, requiring no extra effort from the user (Saez, 2004). An example of passive human power is the Pavegen installation, spanning a 10-square meter area in a London shopping district (Fig7). This innovative technology captures energy from footsteps, illuminating the surroundings and generating ambient bird sounds. Simultaneously, it compiles valuable data on the energy yield.

Furthermore, the walkway interfaces with Bluetooth-enabled phones, offering users rewards such as discounts, vouchers, and educational resources for their pavement-pounding efforts. A standard Pavegen tile, crafted from recycled polymer, employs cutting-edge hybrid black box technology. The piezoelectric effect (generating an electric current when pressure is applied to crystals like quartz) and induction via numerous copper coils and magnets transform kinetic energy from footsteps into electricity. This energy can be stored in a battery or directly supplied to appliances. Compressing around five millimeters upon impact, a single tile produces between one and seven watts. The "Pavegen" is a stellar testament to sustainable technology, generating energy and mitigating pollution while gathering crucial data. This intelligent walkway can also power EnGoPLANET's kinetic/solar streetlights, a creation of the New York-based company. Pedestrian zones prove ideal for installing these lights, directly converting human power into clean and cost-free energy (Wawrla, 2018).

Figure 9: EnGoPLANET Smart Solar/Kinetic Street Lights (Wawrla, et al., 2018).

Another example of human kinetic power generation is in rural areas of Ghana in Africa, where the lack of electricity makes it difficult for children to study and complete homework at night. Therefore, merry-go-rounds are designed to generate electricity for lanterns using human power to address this issue. Children spin it

and create electricity, which powers a battery. Additionally, the battery has solar panels attached to it to avoid battery discharge during school holidays. Every two to three days, rechargeable lanterns are returned to be refilled. The children can learn more about engineering and technology through the merry-go-round's instructive and interactive elements. Students participate in and learn about the production of power (Empowerplaygrounds, 2024).

Another passive form of energy is human body heat. Utilizing body thermal energy in well-insulated buildings is a well-established practice. Spaces with a high influx of people, such as auditoriums, shopping malls, and transit stations, often factor in the heat generated by occupants (Hensel, 2008). For instance, at the Mall of America in Minneapolis, excess body heat from shoppers is harnessed to regulate the temperature of the sprawling complex during Minnesota's harsh winters. Going further, Stockholm station effectively transfers surplus body heat from one building to another using pipes, water, and pumps. The station's ventilation system captures excess body heat from commuters and heats water in underground tanks. This heated water is pumped through pipes to the 13-story Kungbrohuset office building roughly 100 yards away, seamlessly integrating it into the primary heating system. This environmentally conscious and cost-effective system, owned by Jernhusen, the station and office building proprietor, anticipates reducing energy costs in office buildings by up to 20% annually (Content. time, 2022).

4.2 Animal Power (Livestock Body Heat)

Animal power is one of the earliest human ventures into renewable energy sources (Greenenergyhelpfiles, 2022). As mentioned, examples from vernacular architecture illustrate how livestock have historically served as a thermal energy source. A single cow emits approximately 3500 to 4,000 BTU per hour, and the combined heat from 15 cows is sufficient to warm a standard 200-square-foot home. Bryan Ramlow, a former IBM engineer based in Poynette, Wisconsin, pioneered a novel heating system that harnesses cows' body heat. This system functions in a manner like a reverse refrigerator. Heat absorbers collect energy from the livestock, transferring it to a compressor where it is pressurized to raise the temperature. Subsequently, superheated gas flows through heat exchanger units within the living space, elevating the ambient temperature when cool air passes over hot coils. Refer to Fig. (10) for further illustration (Mothererathnews web, 2024).

Fig 10: Bryan's invention can be described as operating like the refrigerator in reverse [18].

5 HARVESTING ALTERNATIVE ENERGY FROM NOISE (ACOUSTIC ENERGY)

Our environment is inundated with noise from airplanes, vehicles, high-speed trains, power plants, loudspeakers, machines, and expressways. Acoustic energy constitutes a pervasive environmental energy source. While ambient sound levels can exceed 100 dB, low-frequency noise prevails daily (Yuan et al., 2019). This presents an opportunity to harness this surplus energy and convert it into a useful resource (Ardiansyah, accessed 2024). Noise barriers can also be ingeniously designed to function as energy harvesters. A developed multifunctional noise barrier that provides sound insulation and harvests acoustic energy. Illustrated in Fig. 11, a PVDF (polyvinylidene difluoride) film, a flexible piezoelectric material, was employed for energy conversion in this application. A single unit can harvest only 0.38 μ W under 100 dB excitation. However, utilizing multiple units to construct a noise barrier can significantly increase harvested power (Zhang et al., 2024).

Fig 11. Components of the AEH unit and the array form create a noise barrier (Wang et al., 2018).

6 CONCLUSIONS

As we face the depletion of fossil fuels, our primary energy source, the imperative to transition towards alternative energy becomes increasingly evident. This shift necessitates a paradigmatic change in urban planning, wherein hybrid urban configurations and strategic spatial arrangements within buildings facilitate energy exchange across various functions, from the city and district scales down to individual buildings. In this innovative approach, even consumers and design challenges metamorphose into energy producers by applying effective strategies. Recent advancements in software development have made it possible to integrate many parameters at the early stages of design. Similarly, a combined effort is now required to seamlessly incorporate alternative energy sources from the project's inception. This holistic approach is paramount in forging a sustainable energy future for generations to come.

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